

"Dual education system: pros and cons"

Aytkulova Guljavkhar

Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology

E-mail: aytikulovaa@gmail.com

Annotation: The article discusses the experience of dual education in Germany, as well as the importance, prospects and advantages of such education in Russia. It also summarizes the differences between bilateral and traditional education systems. Possible sources of funding for bilateral education in the Russian Federation are offered.

Keywords: vocational education, bilateral training of specialists, principles of dual education system, pedagogy of financing dual education; history of pedagogy and education; theory and methods of teaching and education.

Radical changes in Russia's socio-cultural and economic space will inevitably affect education, including vocational education. This is a new approach in the vocational education system that provides quality training for future highly qualified professionals. Strict professional criteria also require increased training of qualified professionals in various fields of life. Today, Russian universities feel the need to modernize and reform higher education. The introduction of a system of bilateral training opens up new additional opportunities to increase the effectiveness of vocational education.

Personnel in a particular field, in our opinion, should be studied qualitatively and quantitatively. We believe that we need to pay attention to the quality aspect and try to consider possible directions to improve the level of education of professionals, what conditions the dual education system meets. The experience of developing education systems in countries such as Sweden, the United Kingdom, Germany, Japan shows the need to combine the learning process and practice, which serves as

a basis for quality training of qualified professionals. Germany was the first country to use the principles of the secondary education system (this system has been in use for 15 years). The implementation of the educational process is carried out by synthesizing production activities as an intern (student) and studying the theoretical part in the educational institution. In addition, there is a gradual complication of learning and practical tasks.

1. A set of possible benefits of dual education

Education in a dual system includes not only educational institutions, but also industrial enterprises, firms, organizations. The programs of the dual education system combine “know-how” tested by theory and practice. The essence of the changes is that students receive simultaneous education in two educational institutions: universities and institutes - in the theoretical part, and in production - in practice. The binary system, as a distinctive feature of the traditional system, implies the exchange of theory and practice throughout the learning period, which leads to the efficiency and effectiveness of the application of the acquired knowledge and skills. The dual education system differs from the vocational education system in that most of the academic week is devoted to internships at the enterprise and a small part (1-2 days) to the university, as a rule, dual education. The education system is also used in technical and socio-economic spheres, construction and engineering. instructions. The binary system has proven itself well in social management, tourism management. Benefits Direct assessment of the faculty by a potential employer Large percentage of employment Maximum approach to production requirements Practical skills in solving production problems are developed High level of motivation for learning Budgeted load reduction Due to the continuous improvement of the training of highly qualified specialists in recent decades, the dual education system has become acceptable in the field of information technology. The practical experience of introducing a dual education system in Germany shows that many areas of training of future professionals are regulated by agreement between social partners, regions and the state. The training

of specialists in a particular field is based on the requirements and requirements of the personnel market, which allows young people to ensure professional mobility and competitiveness. The duration of study varies from 3 years. Interns (students) who have undergone practical training at the enterprise are paid. The system is funded by the state and enterprises. The jurisdiction of the state includes training in this enterprise, and the jurisdiction of the region includes training in a professional university. The company fully equips the educational process with modern equipment that meets the requirements of technology. Large enterprises and organizations have the opportunity to train in their laboratories and workshops, and small ones in the workplace. The initial stage of training is directly related to the internship, and as a result, the graduate is able to demonstrate to a potential employer many years of practical experience in the chosen profession. Under the binary system, a student is the most financially independent because he or she has a small salary during the study period. However, it should be noted that he spent less time studying theory than those who studied in the traditional vocational education system. In our opinion, the possibility of financing from several sources for dual education in Russia should be considered, of course, the bulk of the costs should be covered by the state. The main purpose of non-state funding sources should be to establish the latest training laboratories, sites, workshops with high-level technical and resource equipment for training. Differences between secondary and traditional education systems

Dual teaching system	Traditional teaching system	Reduction of classroom training by up to 30%
Most of the training (up to 70%) is carried out within the walls of the educational institution	The volume of practical training is 60% of the curriculum	Increased to 70%
Practical training is only 25-30% of the training time, and production practice is based on an individual approach, and the current conditions of the nearby enterprise production practice does not meet the needs of employers.	The acquisition of skills is described in the standard of the training profile.	The probability of internship in modern production equipment of direct internship in modern production equipment is about 10%. Acquaintance with corporate culture,

teamwork is not possible in a short time. to get acquainted with the customs and traditions of the enterprise; Scholarships from the company for the entire period of training ia, delivery from work to home The educational process is carried out by the state or by the student himself. topics do not reflect the specifics of production Monitoring is carried out and a list of specialties required by specific teachers in the region is determined. special sciences in the enterprise

Thus, in view of all the above, it should be noted that the main essence of the binary system in the system of vocational education is based on strengthening the practical direction in the training of specialists through the synthesis of educational and production processes. Significantly increases the chances of increasing the professional mobility of graduates of educational institutions. At the same time, it is necessary to remember that the radical changes necessary in the organization of educational activities in the implementation of dual education, the need for adequate integration and integration of theoretical and practical parts throughout the learning process. In addition, the dual education system, in our opinion, is an effective and flexible mechanism that allows to train specialists in high demand by enterprises in various fields in today's market economy.

5. Advantages of dual education.

Dual education for young people in Germany is a great opportunity to achieve independence early and to adapt painlessly to adolescence. While studying, they already receive a cash reward for working in the company, and after graduation - they are very well prepared. The binary system provides easy access to unavoidable stress-free activities for other forms of learning that occur due to lack of information and practical training. It not only allows you to learn to perform specific work tasks, but also develops the ability to work in a team, forming social competence and responsibility.

Significance for the state

The government, which has introduced dual education, is effectively addressing the issue of training qualified personnel. In the German economy, the workload is mainly borne by enterprises. According to statistics, companies spend more than 40 billion euros annually on staff development. This amount significantly exceeds the cost of maintaining universities. The state supports the training of specialists in enterprises by financing the development of the system of vocational schools. The main task of the government is to coordinate the legal framework.

Regulatory support

In Germany, a law regulating vocational education and a “Craft Code” were adopted. These rules regulate the interaction of young people with enterprises and educational institutions. The law defines companies that can participate in dual education. Half a million of the 3.6 million organizations are participating. Regulations on training are adopted by the participants of tariff negotiations - enterprises and staff structures. They came into force at the ministerial level. In turn, the Ministry of Labor will develop a Regulation on Training. This regulates exam requirements.

"Dual education" project: descriptions

The developed model includes educational institutions and regional governments. Co-financing the training of employees for a particular job is carried out by the bodies of companies and entities that order employees for themselves. It should be noted that the country already has a dual education experience. Today, however, programs are being implemented in an unplanned economy. Businesses interested in acquiring highly qualified personnel tend to solve problems on a voluntary basis and share responsibility for training specialists.

Program goals

The development and implementation of the dual education project is aimed at ensuring a modern level of training and retraining of personnel for priority sectors

of advanced high-tech production in the framework of public-private partnership. The main tasks of the program are:

Conclusion

Improving the system of training qualified personnel can be achieved if part of the responsibility falls on the representatives of the business community. At the same time, it is necessary to create a joint zone of cooperation between the state, employers and educational institutions. Experts note that the experience of introducing dual education abroad can be successfully applied in the Russian Federation. Current legislation allows to implement this model taking into account modern conditions. However, the experience of foreign partners undoubtedly requires adaptation in Russia.

However, participants in this training program face a number of challenges:

1. Legislative and regulatory framework governing such a system of training is insufficiently developed.
2. Outdated educational standards apply.
3. No investment (most entrepreneurs are not ready to invest in the training of specialists).

Thus, the relevant ministry faces a number of very important tasks, without which it is impossible to fully implement the DL. Including:

- development of the regulatory framework;
- development of a national model of training in such programs;
- creation of infrastructure for the implementation of dual education (retraining and certification centers, training centers in enterprises);
- Development of a program to monitor the effectiveness of the program.

Solving these problems means creating a new model for training professionals. This narrows the gap between what graduates of educational institutions know and what they know and the requirements placed in different sectors of the economy.

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